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An archway representing Chinatown in Melbourne as a discursively constructed place of otherness

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reviewed by Jaeah Lee

Chinatown was established in Melbourne's central business district during the Victorian gold rush of the 1850s. Often described at the time as a slum (McConville, 1985; Anderson, 1990), it developed into a place where traditional forms of racism were frequently encountered. During the Great Depression of the 1930s, the population declined, and Chinatown was widely perceived as a place destined to disappear (Anderson, 1990). From the 1940s onwards, dwindling shops, markets, and small factories were replaced by restaurants and coffee houses, which attracted people from outside the community, often of Western backgrounds (Geng et al., 2023b,a). In the 1970s and 1980s, the abolition of the White Australia policy contributed to the redevelopment of Chinatown as a multicultural historic precinct. The establishment of the Museum of Chinese Australian History and the promotion of ethnic cultural activities further reinforced its identity as an ethnic enclave and a site of cultural heritage. Today, Chinatown holds a high recognition value and strong tourist appeal, drawing regular visitors from across Melbourne and abroad. It is now considered one of the oldest continuous Chinese settlements in the Western world.

The understanding of Chinatown and its representations can vary greatly. We will in the following follow a poststructural and postcolonial perspective commonly found in critical geography while acknowledging that differing perceptions and conceptualizations of Chinatown exist. From a critical geography perspective, Chinatown is conceptualized as a place of otherness in terms of a constructivist-discursive notion of place (Anderson, 1990). Based on the prevailing understanding of Chinese culture in Western con-

texts, as practised by Western immigrants and their descendants in Melbourne and largely influenced by European ideas and behaviours, the idea of 'Chineseness' has become deeply embedded. It has been primarily discursively constructed, through the continual emphasis and amplification of Chinatown's deviation from Western culture. The further development of Chinatown, framed through this lens of 'Chineseness' and in contrast to Western ideas, has transformed traditional forms of racism into policies of cultural pluralism. However, these policies remain shaped by the exclusionary concept of a mainstream and reinforce a racial frame of reference (Anderson, 1990). These persistent forms of otherness contribute to the marginalization and suppression of cultural minorities, not least through the generalization and differentiation of cultural views and practices, alongside the corresponding exercise of power. In this sense, the social and symbolic production of Chinatown reconfigures existing power relations into new ones, thereby perpetuating colonial narratives.

Stigmatized cultural otherness and associated social exclusion have been transformed into a showcased otherness within the framework of cultural pluralism (Anderson, 1990). To implement a redevelopment plan funded through a City Council grant, a Chinatown Special Advisory Committee was established. The plan sought to emphasize the 'Chineseness' of the area and thereby promote the construction of Chinatown as a place of otherness. To this end, cultural practices were encouraged to demonstrate 'Chineseness', and four archways were erected in 1976 (and later modified) to demarcate Chinatown from its surrounding areas (Geng et al., 2022). The archway on Little

Bourke Street, at the junction with Swanston Street, is one of these four structures and is modelled in its basic appearance on traditional paifangs. As these archways symbolize and exemplify the constructed cultural otherness of this place and were placed at the entrances of Chinatown, they possess strong symbolic saliency and have become emblematic of Chinatown. It is in this sense that Anderson (1990) speaks of ‘cultural relativism in which ancestral culture was being filtered, commodified, and reified by and for white Europeans’. The process of constructing the archways as representations of ‘Chineseness’ thus blends with processes of place-making, which are enacted within a Western context but not necessarily by the residents of Chinatown themselves. The salience of the archways does not, however, necessarily imply their use as a representation of Chinatown. Yet, the archways *are* commonly used as a symbol of Chinatown, such as in travel guides or when people walk past them and point to the archway to refer to the place. This reference is suggested because the archways are not only salient and emblematic of Chinatown but are also typical of this place in the sense that they exemplify ‘Chineseness’, which has influenced Chinatown and transformed it into what it is today.

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